

Spatial Analysis of Crime Patterns in Nigeria (2021-2023): A GIS-Based Approach

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ABSTRACT

This research conducts a spatial inventory of crime in Nigeria. The period of this analysis is from 2021 to 2023, and it studies the spatial pattern and trend of crimes in Nigeria. The crime data was sourced from the official website of Nigeria's Ministry of Police Affairs; the study employs spatial analysis techniques to examine the distribution and concentration of crime across the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The study also employed a mixed-methods approach, a Nigeria digital map was made, the data was downloaded from the official website of the Nigeria's Ministry of Police Affairs, all crime data from the year 2021 – 2023 was imputed into the attribute database of the digital map of Nigeria, present maps showing geographical distribution of crime incidents and also charts and graphs to present statistical data to enable relevant personnel to make meanings out of the data. This study's spatial inventory of crime in Nigeria shows significant results for policymakers, law enforcement agencies, and other stakeholders. These results can inform evidence-based decisions, resource allocation, and crime prevention strategies, ultimately contributing to the reduction of the crime rate and the improvement of national security in Nigeria.

Keywords: Crime, Geographic Information System, Nigeria, Geospatial Analysis, Inventory on Crime.

1. INTRODUCTION

Crimes have been assigned different meanings by different schools of thought as expressed by various authors, but there has not been a singular acceptable definition of crime. Crime is generally understood as a legal wrong for which the offender is punished at the instance of the state. It is an act or omission involving the breach of a duty punishable by indictment in the public interest. Under the Nigerian

Criminal Code Act (Section 2), an act or omission that renders the person doing the act or making the omission liable to punishment under this code, or under any act, law, or statute, is called an offence (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1990). Crime is a social cankerworm that has eaten deep into the social fabric of Nigerian society, such that its effects are multifaceted. Although Durkheim (1958) opines that “crime is an inevitable and normal aspect of social life; it is an integral part of all healthy societies; it is functional” (Haralambos & Holborn, 2008), its functionality in a society such as Nigeria must be viewed seriously because of the social and psychological problems it has caused many victims. In fact, no matter the functionality of crime in society, the act of crime is condemnable and unacceptable in a healthy society, regardless of the justification criminals may present. As Martin Luther King Jr. (1963) aptly stated, darkness cannot drive out darkness; only light can do that. Hate cannot drive out hate; only love can do that. From 2021 to 2023, the prevalent crimes in Nigeria included kidnapping, murder, armed robbery, terrorism/secessionist activities, armed banditry, and other criminal activities, which have become the order of the day (Nigeria Ministry of Police Affairs, 2023). The police are responsible for ensuring internal security by safeguarding lives and property. However, the question remains: “Have the police been able to carry out their functions effectively and efficiently?” It is worth recalling that in 2019, Operation Puff Adder was launched by the Nigerian police to tackle banditry, kidnapping, and other violent crimes in northern Nigeria. This operation resulted in the arrest of numerous criminals and the recovery of illegal arms. It was commended for its focus on intelligence gathering and tactical operations (Nigeria Police Force, 2019).

2. Materials and Methods

Hardware

- i. HP Folio with 500 GB hard drive and 16 GB of RAM
- ii. Dell latitude with 256 SSD and 8 GB ram

Software

The following software was used;

- i. ArcGIS 10.8

- ii. Microsoft Office
- iii. QGIS 3.6
- iv. Google Chrome

The materials used in this study include both hardware and software resources. The HP Folio with a 500 GB hard drive and 16 GB of RAM was used for intensive GIS operations such as spatial data processing, map rendering, and geostatistical analysis due to its higher memory capacity. The Dell Latitude with a 256 GB SSD and 8 GB of RAM was employed for data entry, documentation, and moderate GIS tasks. Its solid-state drive ensured faster file access and application performance, making it suitable for tasks that did not require heavy processing power.

The software used in this study included ArcGIS 10.8, QGIS 3.6, Microsoft Office, and Google Chrome. ArcGIS 10.8 was used for core spatial analysis, including georeferencing crime data, performing spatial queries, generating crime hotspot maps, and producing final map layouts. QGIS 3.6, as an open-source alternative, supported the preprocessing and visualization of spatial data and provided additional plugin-based tools for spatial inventory. Microsoft Office was used for organizing raw crime report data in spreadsheets, compiling results, and preparing charts and written reports. Google Chrome was employed to access online crime databases, download spatial datasets, and consult web-based GIS tools or references relevant to the study.

Fig 1. Methodological flowchart

2.1. Data Acquisition

For this study, data sets such as the administrative boundary shapefile for all the states in Nigeria, alongside the crime statistics (Terrorism/Secessionist Attacks, Armed Banditry, Murder Cases, Armed Robbery Cases, Kidnapping Cases) from 2021 to 2023, were acquired. The datasets were selected based on criteria designed to enhance the depth of the investigation. These datasets were incorporated into an ArcMap geodatabase. The data used for this research was sourced from reports of the Ministry of Police Affairs Planning Research and Statistics Department and entered into the ArcGIS attribute table environment to update the collected shapefile from OSGOF. Various cartographic tools were utilized for visualization in Quantum GIS (QGIS). This project relied solely on secondary data.

MINISTRY OF POLICE AFFAIRS
PLANNING RESEARCH AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT
CRIME STATISTICS ACROSS THE NATION FROM NIGERIA POLICE FORCE

SUMMARY ON MAJOR CRIMES RECORDED ACROSS THE NATION FROM 1ST JANUARY TO DECEMBER 2021

S/NO.	GEO-POLITICAL ZONES	STATE	CRIMES					TOTAL	REMARK
			TERRORISM/ SECESSIONISTS ATTACK	ARMED BANDITRY	MURDER CASES	ARMED ROBBERY CASES	KIDNAPPING CASES		
			JAN . DEC	JAN . DEC	JAN . DEC	JAN . DEC	JAN . DEC		
			OCCURRENCE						
1	NORTH CENTRAL	KOGI			28	7	26	61	NO CRIME RECORDED FROM BAUCHI, KATSINA AND YOBE STATES FROM JANUARY TO DECEMBER, 2021 SOME DAILY NATIONAL CRIME REPORTS WERE NOT SENT TO PLANNING, RESEARCH AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT
		BENUE			110	19	18	147	
		KWARA			38	8	20	66	
		NASARAWA			27	11	18	56	
		PLATEAU			71	10	49	130	
		FCT		1	84	24	72	161	
		NIGER		22	92	40	93	247	
2	NORTH EAST	BORNO	38		36	6	6	86	
		ADAMAWA			4		1	5	
		GOEMBE			10	1	3	14	
		TARABA	2		36	14	24	76	
3	NORTH WEST	KADUNA	10	94	211	35	228	578	
		JIGAWA			11	2	9	22	
		KEBBI		27	55	15	36	133	
		SOKOTO	2	28	93	67	93	283	
		ZAMFARA	2	14	67	15	40	138	
		KANO			3	6	4	13	
4	SOUTH EAST	EBONYI	2	1	24	7	5	39	
		IMO	8	1	62	28	38	137	
		ENUGU	22	2	45	34	30	133	
		ABIA	2		34	13	27	76	
		ANAMBRA	17	2	50	6	8	83	
5	SOUTH SOUTH	CROSS RIVER			10	6	10	26	
		AKWA IBOM			17	6	4	27	
		DELTA			70	59	39	168	
		RIVERS			42	24	30	96	
		BAYELSA			29	18	18	65	
		EDO		120	44	127		291	
6	SOUTH WEST	OTO			178	102	56	336	
		OGUN			16	11	16	43	
		ONDO					1	1	
		OSUN			45	14	9	68	
		LAGOS			62	14	2	78	
		EKITI			27	11	24	62	
TOTAL			105	312	1731	760	1057	3965	

Fig. 2. Snippet on major crime across the nation from 1st of January to December 2021

Source: Ministry of Police Affairs

MINISTRY OF POLICE AFFAIRS
PLANNING RESEARCH AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT
CRIME STATISTICS ACROSS THE NATION FROM NIGERIA POLICE FORCE
SUMMARY ON MAJOR CRIMES RECORDED ACROSS THE NATION FROM 1ST JANUARY TO DECEMBER 2022

S/NO.	GEO-POLITICAL ZONES	STATE	CRIMES						TOTAL	REMARK
			TERRORISM/ SECESSIONISTS ATTACK	ARMED BANDITRY	MURDER CASES	ARMED ROBBERY CASES	KIDNAPPING CASES	OTHERS		
			JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC		
1	NORTH CENTRAL	KOGI		5	38	6	78	17	149	NO CRIME RECORDED FROM BAUCHI AND YOBE STATES FROM JANUARY TO DECEMBER, 2022
		BENUE	5	2	63	7	22	12	106	
		KWARA		2	36	18	10	4	70	
		NASARAWA	3	1	20	8	20	10	62	
		PLATEAU	5	5	21	9	73	18	126	
		FCT	1	6	35	29	67	98	236	
		NIGER	6	109	102	38	117	6	378	
2	NORTH EAST	BORNO	79	1	83	19	31	25	238	SOME DAILY NATIONAL CRIME REPORTS WERE NOT SENT TO PLANNING, RESEARCH AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT
		ADAMAWA		1	2	3	4	3	13	
		GOMBE			11	3	3	2	19	
3	NORTH WEST	TARABA	2	2	40	7	53	32	136	
		KADUNA	10	347	257	44	370	41	1059	
		JIGAWA		2	7	2	8	3	22	
		KERRI	4	32	46	8	59	22	171	
		KATSINA	29	124	101	36	168	23	481	
		SOKOTO	2	109	75	19	208	13	426	
		ZAMFARA	7	206	80	41	109	17	460	
4	SOUTH EAST	KANO		1	6	7	12	9	35	
		EBONYI	11		11		3		27	
		IMO	29	4	39	15	19	10	116	
		ENUGU	43	3	117	58	73	45	339	
		ABIA	8		18	25	21	5	77	
		AKHIRA	64	1	11	30	35	15	156	
		CROSS RIVER	2		1	1	1	1	6	
5	SOUTH SOUTH	AKWA IBOM	3		38	15	14	12	68	
		DELTA	8	1	1	16	31	30	77	
		RIVERS	1	2	38	17	46	30	114	
		BAYELSA	8		25	17	17	8	67	
		EDO		4	99	43	131	39	318	
6	SOUTH WEST	OYO	3		122	74	46	49	294	
		OSUN		1	10	4	17	5	37	
		ONDO			7	7	27	17	58	
		OSUN	1		53	14	8	16	92	
		LAGOS	2	3	120	36	6	103	270	
		EKITI			5	1	6	2	21	
TOTAL			320	974	1722	679	1925	739	6359	

Fig 3. Snippet on major crime across the nation from 1st of January to December 2021

Source: Ministry of Police Affairs

MINISTRY OF POLICE AFFAIRS
PLANNING RESEARCH AND STATISTICS DEPARTMENT
CRIME STATISTICS ACROSS THE NATION FROM NIGERIA POLICE FORCE
SUMMARY OF MAJOR CRIMES RECORDED ACROSS THE NATION FROM 1ST JANUARY TO 31ST DECEMBER 2023

ANNEXURE 1

S/NO.	GEO-POLITICAL ZONES	STATE	CRIMES						TOTAL	REMARK
			TERRORISM/S SECESSIONIST CASES	BANDITRY/C ASES	MURDER CASES	ARMED ROBBERY CASES	KIDNAPPING CASES	OTHER OFFENCES		
			JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC	JAN - DEC		
1	NORTH CENTRAL	KOGI	2		22	1	97	15	147	THERE WAS A KIDNAPPING REPORT CASES IN ALL OVER THE COUNTRY FROM JANUARY TO DECEMBER 2023.
		BENUE		2	5	6	11	12	43	
		NASARAWA	1		17	4	43	11	72	
		KWARA	1		14	4	33	4	56	
		PLATEAU	5		230	14	119	65	433	
		FCT	2	2	43	22	132	112	311	
		NIGER	2	15	48	7	41	31	134	
2	NORTH EAST	TARABA	1	1	155	10	200	25	392	
		ADAMAWA	1		29	2	39	19	91	
		BAUCHI	5	1	14	1	22	6	43	
		YOBE	5	1	18	2	11	17	51	
		GOMBE	2	1	30	10	74	28	145	
		BORNO	58		99		62	25	244	
		KADUNA	1	28	139	14	310	71	563	
3	NORTH WEST	KERRI	2	12	91	2	84	22	213	
		KANO	1		35	8	17	39	99	
		KATSINA	18	35	46	2	133	24	258	
		JIGAWA							1	
		SOKOTO	1	11	33	2	50	8	105	
		ZAMFARA	3	27	73	1	160	19	283	
		EBONYI	1		11	1	17	18	47	
4	SOUTH EAST	AKHIRA	12		14	1	10	22	59	
		ENUGU	6	3	67	17	69	64	217	
		ABIA	3		38	17	32	23	137	
		AKWA IBOM	9		38	8	43	13	111	
		CROSS RIVER			11	3	17	9	40	
		AKWA IBOM	1		24	5	7	23	59	
		RIVERS	1		14	15	39	23	99	
5	SOUTH SOUTH	DELTA			16	11	47	19	93	
		BAYELSA			17	2	5	20	51	
		EDO	1	1	79	14	97	61	253	
		OYO	1	1	64	31	16	62	176	
		OSUN			12	13	15	13	53	
		ONDO			25	5	20	39	89	
		OSUN	1		38	15	30	27	111	
6	SOUTH WEST	LAGOS	1		35	32	4	105	177	
		OSUN			35	11	6	57	98	
		EKITI			5	1	6	2	21	
TOTAL			141	138	1798	320	2149	1161	5647	

SOURCE: POLICE FORCE HEADQUARTER - DAILY NATIONAL CRIME REPORT

Fig 4. Snippet on major crime across the nation from 1st of January to December 2021

Source: Ministry of Police Affairs

2.2. Data Processing and Mapping Procedures

The crime statistics reports published by the Ministry of Police Affairs, Planning, Research, and Statistics Department for the years 2021 to 2023 were examined to assess the reliability and completeness of the data. Despite potential issues that could affect data quality, every effort was made to ensure a high standard of accuracy. To support this, the GIS software (ArcGIS and QGIS) used in the analysis was updated to the latest available versions. The accuracy and reliability of the reported crime data significantly influenced the overall quality of the spatial inventory produced. All data downloaded for the study were sourced from verifiable and traceable origins and obtained at the highest possible resolution. During the preliminary examination, some inconsistencies were detected in the acquired data, such as the misclassification of states within incorrect geopolitical zones. These errors were systematically corrected to ensure accurate representation and reliable interpretation of the research results. The data preparation phase involved the extraction, processing, and integration of various datasets obtained from multiple sources to derive meaningful conclusions. A key step in this process was creating a crime inventory database by updating the administrative map of Nigerian states with the corresponding number of reported crime incidents for each year from 2021 to 2023. Additionally, QGIS symbology tools were employed to visually enhance the maps, enabling a clear presentation of the spatial distribution of crime events. To develop the inventory of crime occurrences, data from the Ministry's reports were first compiled and organized using Microsoft Excel. These records were then used to update an existing shapefile of Nigeria.

3. STUDY AREA

Nigeria is located in West Africa, bordering the Gulf of Guinea, between Benin and Cameroon. It lies between latitudes 4° and 14° north of the equator and longitudes 3° and 15° east of the Greenwich meridian, Nigeria is a federal republic consisting of 36 states and the federal capital territory (FCT), Abuja. As of 2020, Nigeria's estimated population is approximately 202 million people, with an annual

growth rate of 2.6%. Nigeria has a tropical climate, with temperatures ranging from 22°C to 30°C (72°F to 86°F) throughout the year. The country has two main seasons: the rainy season (May-October) and the dry season (November-April). Nigeria has a mixed economy, Nigeria is the 12th largest producer of petroleum in the world, agriculture is a significant sector, employing about 70% of the labor force, manufacturing: Nigeria has a growing manufacturing sector, with industries like textiles, food processing, and cement production. Major crops include cassava, yam, sorghum, maize rice e.t.c. The study will utilize crime data from the Nigeria’s ministry of police affairs. The data covers crime including kidnapping, murder, terrorism/secessionist, banditry, armed robbery and other crimes.

Figure 5. Map of Nigeria showing the geopolitical zone
 Source: maps-nigeria.com

4. Result Presentation

This section presents the analysis of the data gathered during the study, including the modeling of the associated database. To enhance clarity and facilitate interpretation, the findings are displayed using maps, charts, and tables where appropriate. The outputs from this study were converted into geospatial datasets by integrating the crime data with the political-administrative boundaries of Nigeria’s thirty-

six (36) states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The crime inventory—comprising categories such as Terrorism/Secessionist Attacks, Armed Banditry, Murder, Armed Robbery, and Kidnapping—was obtained from the reports of the Ministry of Police Affairs Planning, Research, and Statistics Department. These data are presented in tabular form and visualized through a spatial database developed using QGIS software. In total, 15,971 crime incidents were recorded between 2021 and 2023.

4.1. Data presentation for Crime Inventory in Nigeria for 2021

The processed statistics were mapped to facilitate spatial understanding of crime distribution across the country. The 2021 crime data reveal notable variations in incident frequency among states. States such as Ondo, Adamawa, Gombe, Jigawa, and Kano reported low crime levels, each recording fewer than 15 incidents. States like Cross River, Abia, Ekiti, Nasarawa, Taraba, Bayelsa, and Kwara exhibited moderate crime levels, with reported incidents ranging between 15 and 80. In contrast, Lagos, Osun, Rivers, Plateau, and Sokoto experienced elevated crime rates, recording between 80 and 300 incidents. The most severely affected states in 2021 included Niger, Kaduna, Zamfara, and Edo, each reporting over 200 incidents. Notably, Kaduna recorded the highest number of incidents, with a total of 578. These patterns underscore the severity of insecurity in certain regions, often influenced by proximity to high-risk areas, porous borders, and socio-economic challenges such as high unemployment rates. Furthermore, the spatial distribution reveals regional clustering of similar crime frequencies, suggesting a level of interdependence among neighboring states in terms of security dynamics. This reinforces the importance of interstate collaboration in tackling shared security threats and enhancing national safety.

Crimes Cases Recorded Across the Nation From 1st January to December 2021						
State	Terro rism	Armed Banditry	Murder Cases	Armed Robbery Cases	Kidnapping Cases	Total
Abia	2		34	13	27	76
Abuja		1	84	24	72	181
Adamawa			4		1	5
Akwa- Ibom			17	6	4	27
Anambra	17	2	50	6	8	83
Bauchi						
Bayelsa			29	18	18	65
Benue			110	19	18	147
Borno	38		36	6	6	86
Cross- River			10	6	10	26
Delta			70	59	39	168
Ebonyi	2	1	24	7	5	39
Edo		120	44	127		291
Ekiti			27	11	24	62
Enugu	22	2	45	34	30	133
Gombe			10	1	3	14
Imo	8	1	62	28	38	137
Jigawa			11	2	9	22
Kaduna	10	94	211	35	228	578
Kano			3	6	4	13
Katsina						
Kebbi		27	55	15	36	133
Kogi			28	7	26	61
Kwara			38	8	20	66
Lagos			62	14	2	78
Nasarawa			27	11	18	56
Niger		22	92	40	93	247
Ogun			16	11	16	43
Ondo					1	1
Osun			45	14	9	68
Oyo			178	102	56	336
Plateau			71	10	49	130
Rivers			42	24	30	96
Sokoto	2	28	93	67	93	283
Taraba	2		36	14	24	76
Yobe						
Zamfara	2	14	67	15	40	138
Total	105	312	1731	760	1057	3965

Table 1. Table showing the Crime Inventory across States in Nigeria for 2021

Fig 7. Bar Chart showing the Total crime cases across States in Nigeria in 2021

Fig. 8. Pie Chart showing the Total crime cases across States in Nigeria in 2021

4.2. Data presentation for Crime Inventory in Nigeria for 2022

The spatial pattern of crime incidents across Nigeria in 2022, as illustrated in Figure 4.3, reveals considerable disparities among the states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). A total of 6,359 crime events were recorded during the year, with the frequency of occurrences varying significantly due to regional dynamics and socio-economic conditions. The states with the highest crime figures were Kaduna, Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, and Niger, with Kaduna leading at 1,069 incidents. This concentration of criminal activity underscores the ongoing security crises in the North West and North Central regions, where issues such as banditry, communal clashes, and kidnapping remain prevalent. The geographical proximity of these states and the persistence of regional instability likely contribute to the elevated crime rates observed. In the next tier, states including Lagos, the FCT (Abuja), Kano, Rivers, and Borno reported between 200 and 500 incidents. This group reflects the challenges associated with urban security and, in cases like Borno, the residual effects of insurgency. These urban centers are often faced with complex social dynamics and higher population densities, which increase vulnerability to crime. States such as Kogi, Bayelsa, Enugu, Taraba, Oyo, Edo, and Benue experienced moderate crime levels, ranging from 70 to 200 incidents. While not classified as hotspots, these areas remain susceptible to intermittent criminal activity due to factors such as their location, economic relevance, and population flow. At the lower end of the crime spectrum, states including Ekiti, Ondo, Cross River, Gombe, Ogun, and Jigawa reported between 20 and 70 incidents. These relatively low numbers may be attributed to effective security strategies, less urban congestion, or lower crime-attracting activities. Finally, Yobe, Adamawa, and Kebbi recorded fewer than 20 crime incidents in 2022, reflecting a relatively stable and secure environment. These states consistently report minimal crime activity, as seen in previous years, reinforcing their status as low-risk areas.

Overall, the 2022 data continue to highlight persistent insecurity in northern Nigeria, particularly in the North West due to escalating banditry. It also points to urban-centered crime challenges in parts of the South West and South-South. These trends emphasize the necessity for targeted, region-specific approaches to addressing the root causes of crime and improving public safety.

Fig 9. Map showing crime rate across states in Nigeria

Cross-River	2		8	3	13	9	35
Delta	8	1	1	16	31	20	77
Ebonyi	11		11		3	2	27
Edo		4	99	43	131	39	316
Ekiti			5	1	6	9	21
Enugu	43	3	117	58	73	45	339
Gombe			11	3	3	2	19
Imo	29	4	39	15	19	10	116
Jigawa		2	7	2	8	3	22
Kaduna	10	347	257	44	370	41	1069
Kano		1	6	7	12	9	35
Katsina	29	124	101	36	168	23	481
Kebbi	4	32	46	8	59	22	171
Kogi	5	5	38	6	78	17	149
Kwara		2	36	18	10	4	70
Lagos	2	3	120	36	6	103	270
Nasarawa	3	1	20	8	20	10	62
Niger	6	109	102	38	117	6	378
Ogun		1	10	4	17	5	37
Ondo			7	7	27	17	58
Osun	1		53	14	8	16	92
Oyo	3		122	74	46	49	294
Plateau		5	21	9	73	18	126
Rivers	1	2	28	17	46	20	114
Sokoto	2	109	75	19	208	13	426
Taraba	2	2	40	7	53	32	136
Yobe							
Zamfara	7	206	80	41	109	17	460
Total	320	974	1722	679	1925	739	6359

Table 2. Table showing the Crime Inventory across States in Nigeria for 2022

Fig 10. Bar Chart showing the crime rate cases across States in Nigeria in 2022

Fig 11. Pie Chart showing the crime rate cases across States in Nigeria in 2022

4.3. Data presentation for Crime Inventory in Nigeria for 2023

The crime data for 2023 reveals a notable decline in reported incidents, with a total of 5,647 cases recorded across all 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), compared to 6,359 in 2022. This decrease suggests some level of improvement in national security and the effectiveness of crime prevention strategies. States such as Jigawa, Cross River, Bayelsa, and Ebonyi recorded the lowest crime figures, each with fewer than 60 reported incidents, reaffirming their position among the safest areas in the country. Jigawa, in particular, stood out with just six recorded incidents, maintaining its consistent trend of low criminal activity. Moderate crime levels, with figures between 50 and 100, were observed in states like Bauchi, Ondo, Benue, and Yobe. These numbers reflect relatively stable security conditions, likely influenced by ongoing law enforcement efforts and active community participation. However, some of these states, especially those in border regions like Taraba and Benue, still face intermittent security challenges, underscoring the need for sustained vigilance. States such as Lagos, Kogi, Ogun, and Enugu reported between 100 and 200 incidents, indicating moderate levels of crime. Lagos, despite being Nigeria's commercial hub and thus prone to urban crime, showed some improvement compared to 2022. Kogi's position along key transportation routes continues to make it vulnerable to crimes such as armed robbery and kidnapping, necessitating targeted strategies to strengthen its security framework. Higher crime rates were still evident in Kaduna, Zamfara, Katsina, Taraba, and Plateau. These states together contributed a significant portion of the national total. Kaduna, with 563 incidents, remained one of the most affected states due to persistent issues like banditry and kidnapping. Although there was a slight decline in incidents compared to the previous year, these states continue to face serious security threats that require focused interventions. In southern Nigeria, states such as Delta and Edo also reported relatively high crime figures, primarily driven by kidnapping, armed robbery, and other violent crimes. While the numbers have dropped compared to 2022, the root causes—such as unemployment, inequality, and poverty—still fuel criminal behavior in these areas. The overall decline in crime incidents in 2023 signals progress in the fight against insecurity across Nigeria. However, the concentration of crime in certain regions, particularly the North

West, North Central, and parts of the South South, highlights the ongoing need for sustained and adaptive security strategies. Long-term solutions must combine enhanced law enforcement with socio-economic reforms and community-based initiatives to ensure continued improvement in public safety.

Fig. 12. Map showing the crime rate cases across States in Nigeria in 2023

Fig 13. Bar Chart showing the crime rate cases across States in Nigeria in 2023

Crimes Cases Recorded Across the Nation From 1st January to December 2023							
State	Terrorism Cases	Banditry Cases	Murder Cases	Armed Robbery Cases	Kidnapping Cases	Other Offences	Total
Abia			36	17	32	52	137
Abuja		2	43	22	132	112	311

Adamawa	1		29	3	39	19	91
Akwa Ibom			24	5	7	23	59
Anambra	12		21	8	17	18	76
Bauchi			14	1	22	6	43
Bayelsa			17	5	9	20	51
Benue		2	52	6	11	12	83
Borno	58		99		62	25	244
Cross- River			11	3	17	9	40
Delta			16	11	47	19	93
Ebonyi	6	1	14	1	10	22	54
Edo	1	1	79	14	97	61	253
Ekiti			36	11	14	37	98
Enugu	6		60	17	99	64	246
Gombe	2	1	30	10	74	28	145
Imo	9		38	8	33	23	111
Jigawa					5	1	6
Kaduna	1	28	139	14	310	71	563
Kano			35	8	17	39	99
Katsina	18	35	46	2	133	24	258
Kebbi	2	12	91	2	84	22	213
Kogi	2		32	1	97	15	147
Kwara	1		14	4	33	4	56
Lagos	1		35	32	4	105	177
Nasarawa	1		17		43	11	72
Niger	2	15	48	7	41	21	134
Ogun			12	13	15	13	53
Ondo			25	5	20	39	89
Osun	1		38	15	30	27	111
Oyo	1	1	64	31	16	62	175
Plateau	5		230	14	119	65	433
Rivers	1		14	15	39	23	92
Sokoto	1	11	33	2	50	8	105
Taraba	1	1	155	10	200	25	392
Yobe	5	1	18	2	11	17	54
Zamfara	3	27	73	1	160	19	283
Total	141	138	1738	320	2149	1161	5647

Table 3. Showing the Crime Inventory for the States in Nigeria for 2023

Fig. 14. Pie Chart showing the Total crime rate cases across states in Nigeria in 2023

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This research has effectively demonstrated the use of geospatial methodologies to develop a comprehensive spatial inventory of criminal activities across Nigeria from 2021 to 2023. By utilizing Geographic Information System (GIS) tools such as ArcGIS and QGIS, crime data were not only compiled but also visualized spatially, enabling a clearer understanding of the distribution, frequency, and trends of criminal incidents across the 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).

The crime data used in this study were sourced from the Ministry of Police Affairs, and the analysis included a spatial adjustment of Nigeria's political-administrative map to correct errors such as the misplacement of states within incorrect geopolitical zones. This data correction was essential to ensure an accurate representation of regional crime patterns.

The findings revealed notable trends across the three years:

- i. In 2021, states like Ondo, Adamawa, and Gombe recorded relatively low crime figures, whereas states such as Lagos, Osun, Rivers, Plateau, and Sokoto experienced significantly higher crime rates.
- ii. In 2022, the North West and North Central zones emerged as the most affected regions, with states like Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, and Kaduna recording the highest crime rates. Meanwhile, states such as Ekiti, Ondo, Cross River, Gombe, Ogun, and Jigawa reported the lowest figures.
- iii. By 2023, although there was a reduction in total crime incidents nationwide (5,647 cases compared to 6,359 in 2022), states such as Kaduna, Zamfara, Katsina, Taraba, and Plateau remained among the most affected. States like Bauchi, Ondo, Benue, and Yobe continued to show relatively low crime rates, indicating some progress in security efforts.

When examined by crime type:

- i. Terrorism-related incidents increased dramatically from 105 cases in 2021 to 320 in 2022, with states like Borno, Enugu, Anambra, and Katsina heavily affected. However, in 2023, terrorism cases dropped to 141, potentially reflecting improved counterterrorism strategies.
- ii. Armed banditry saw a sharp increase from 312 cases in 2021 to 974 in 2022, indicating a wider spread and entrenchment of this form of violence. States most affected included Kaduna, Zamfara, Katsina, Niger, and Sokoto.
- iii. Murder cases remained consistently high across the three years, with 1,731 cases in 2021, 1,722 in 2022, and 1,738 in 2023. The states most affected varied slightly each year, but Kaduna consistently reported high figures, along with Plateau, Niger, Lagos, and Borno.
- iv. Armed robbery incidents decreased over time, from 760 in 2021 to 679 in 2022 and down to 320 in 2023. Despite this decline, Lagos, Oyo, Edo, and Anambra remained critical hotspots.
- v. Kidnapping emerged as one of the most severe and escalating crimes. From 1,057 cases in 2021, the numbers nearly doubled to 1,925 in 2022 and rose further to 2,145 in 2023. Northern states

such as Kaduna, Sokoto, and Niger consistently experienced the highest rates, indicating the endemic nature of kidnapping in those regions.

The comprehensive use of GIS in this research allowed for the effective mapping and analysis of crime trends, which are invaluable in identifying patterns, hotspots, and regional vulnerabilities. This spatial intelligence is not only beneficial for academic purposes but also holds immense value for national security planning and policymaking.

Recommendations

- i. Enhanced Integration of GIS in Security Planning:** Security agencies should adopt GIS technology as a standard tool for crime mapping, hotspot detection, and tactical deployment of resources.
- ii. Targeted Security Interventions:** Areas identified as persistent crime hotspots, especially in the North West and North Central zones, should be prioritized for special intervention programs, including improved intelligence gathering and community policing.
- iii. Strengthening Counterterrorism and Anti-Kidnapping Measures:** The consistent rise in terrorism and kidnapping calls for a more robust, coordinated response involving both federal and state governments.
- iv. Data Transparency and Accessibility:** The Ministry of Police Affairs and other relevant institutions should ensure the continuous and public availability of reliable crime data to support research, policy formulation, and public accountability.
- v. Socio Economic Development Initiatives:** Since many crimes are linked to poverty, unemployment, and poor governance, holistic development strategies that improve education, create jobs, and strengthen institutions are essential for long-term security.

- vi. **Regional Collaboration:** States within shared high-crime corridors should collaborate more closely in intelligence sharing and cross-border crime prevention to combat the mobility of criminal elements.
- vii. **Community Engagement and Sensitization:** Citizens must be engaged in the fight against crime through awareness programs, neighborhood watch schemes, and improved trust between communities and law enforcement.

In conclusion, this study has shown that geospatial technology is not only effective in analyzing crime data but is also vital in crafting evidence-based strategies for crime prevention and management. By leveraging these insights, security agencies and policymakers can adopt more informed, proactive, and region-specific approaches to reduce crime and enhance safety across Nigeria.

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